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APPLICATION OF MULTISTAGE SURGICAL TACTICS IN EMERGENCY SURGERY FOR COMBINED ABDOMINAL TRAUMA

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SUMMARY: The authors proposed active surgical tactics as "damage control" in traumatic liver injuries. The method of "damage control" in SFRICAN used since 2009 as the only method of saving the life of patients with traumatic injuries of the liver in the IV and V degree (for E. Moore, 1986). In the departments of emergency surgery STRNCMP 2009–2019 130 operated patients with liver trauma.

Of these, 19 (14.61%) patients with severe liver injuries of IV and V degree of damage by E. Moore. The effectiveness of multi-stage tactics was evaluated by the level of mortality and the number of purulent-septic complications.

The results of surgical treatment of 19 patients with massive liver injuries, aged 17 to 50 years, were analyzed. The median age was 26 ± 2.0 years. There were 11 men and 8 women. The average assessment of the severity of damage on the ISS scale was 34 points (17-76), E. Moore IV and V degree of damage. The average blood loss was 2850 ml (1750-3850 ml). All patients underwent multi-stage laparotomy with gauze (film) tamponade, the average number of operations per 1 person 2.7 (2-5), suturing of the liver wound with tamponade (13), extensive hepatotomy and vascular ligation (3), atypical resection (2), stitching of large major vessels with taponade (1). The average bed/day in the intensive care unit is 13 (3-16), and the average bed/day in the clinic is 25 (3-28). Mortality was 26.3% (5 out of 19), mainly purulent-septic complications and multiple organ failure. Multi-stage surgical tactics "damage control" in isolated and combined severe liver damage is an effective method in unstable patients with the risk of developing coagulopathy and multiple organ failure.

The use of the "damage control" technique helped to reduce mortality rate from acute abdominal pathology by 26.3%.

Keywords: closed abdominal trauma, liver injury, "damage control".

Relevance. Traumatic liver injuries are considered the most dangerous among injuries of the abdominal organs due to the severity of their course, the complexity of diagnosis and treatment, and their high mortality rate. The frequency of liver injuries in closed abdominal trauma ranges from 20 to 46.9% [2,3,11,23], with penetrating injuries - from 57% to 86.4% of observations [12,17].

According to literature data, postoperative mortality in closed abdominal trauma with liver damage is 30.4%, in case of stab wounds of the organ - from 4 to 10.5%, in case of combined trauma, 39.3% of patients die. those who suffered [1,5,14,15,21,22].

In modern combined trauma, victims whose severity of injuries on a scale ISS corresponds to grades IV and V (according to E. Moore, 1986), characterized by high mortality, reaching 40-80%. High mortality rates are associated with a combination of injuries, shock, and blood loss, aggravated in the early postoperative period by the development of "abdominal compartment syndrome," and subsequently by purulent-septic complications [4,6,7,8,13,16,17].

Traditional surgical tactics for isolated and combined injuries include laparotomy with correction of existing injuries to the abdominal and thoracic cavities. However, with massive damage to internal organs, often combined with damage to large vessels, complete correction of all damage takes a lot of time, which affects the outcome of treatment [9, 10, 11, 12, 18, 19, and 20].

Initially, the "damage control" strategy (M. Rotondo 1993) was used for the surgical treatment of wounded patients with polytrauma. This technique consisted of three stages [23]:

The first is an emergency, immediate surgical intervention to stop active bleeding and prevent infection of the abdominal cavity.

The second is the implementation of cumulative intensive anti-shock therapy in the presence of an intensive care unit for the fastest rehabilitation of the body.

Third - within 48-72 hours after injury, the final decision on surgical treatment is made.

Purpose of the study-evaluate the effectiveness of the method "damage control" for severe liver damage.

Materials and methods. In the emergency surgery departments of the SFRNCEMP, 130 patients with liver trauma were operated on in 2009–2019.

Of these, 19 (14.61%) of victims with severe liver injuries of IV and V degrees of damage according to E. Moore. The effectiveness of multi-stage tactics was assessed by the level of mortality and the number of purulent-septic complications.

Were The results of surgical treatment of 19 patients with massive liver damage, aged from 17 to 50 years, were studied. Average age 26 years. Of these, 11 are men and 8 are women. The average score of injury severity on the ISS scale was 34 points (17-76), according to E. Moore, grades IV and V of injury. The average blood loss was 2850 ml (1750-3850 ml). All patients underwent multi-stage laparotomy with gauze (film) tamponade, the average number of operations per 1 person was 2.7 (2-5), suturing of a liver wound with tamponade (13), extensive hepatotomy and ligation of blood vessels (3), atypical resection (2), suturing large main vessels with taponade (1). The average bed/day in the intensive care

unit is 13 (3-16), and the average bed/day in the clinic is 25 (3-28). Mortality was 26.3% (5 out of 19), mainly purulent-septic complications and multiple organ failure.

In addition, a correlation study was carried out: 41 patients with acute abdominal pathology, treated using the “damage control” system (interrupted surgery), 30 patients (control group, similar in main nosology, time of hospitalization, concomitant nosology, age) were treated using the “early total care” (simultaneous implementation of the full scope of surgical intervention, regardless of the type of nosology and primary condition of the patient).

To understand the severity of the patient and the legitimacy of managing patients in the “damage control” mode, a scale was designed (each indicator was scored from 1 to 4 points) of the patient’s nosology:

< 9 points – there are no indications for using the “damage control” technique,

10-16 points are clear indications for “damage control”.

Empiricism in decision making is acceptable for neighboring algorithm values of 8-9 points.

In the severity scale, these indicators were taken into account: the duration of the disease, the source of peritonitis, the type of inflammatory and destructive processes in the abdominal cavity, in case of mesenteric-vascular thrombosis the degree of intestinal necrosis was taken into account, in case of acute intestinal obstruction - the origin of the obstruction, in the circumstances of infected pancreatic necrosis - generalization and the location of the process, the presence of shock in polytrauma with damage to the abdominal organs, etc. was taken into account.

There is no doubt that an important and decisive point in this tactic is to perform not a single surgical intervention, but 2 or more according to indications.

Results and discussion. The mortality rate in the main group of patients with the “damage control” technique was 19.5% (8 out of 41 patients died). This coefficient in the comparative group with the “early total care” technique was 53.3% (16 out of 30 patients died).

The study of the first steps of this tactic and the final data obtained were the predetermining factor for creating our own scale in order to take into account the operational risk, as well as further prognosis of the disease based on the physiological state of the patient. The following were taken into account: the patient’s age, blood pressure (mmHg), heart rate (beats/min), Hb (hemoglobin) g/l, Potassium (mmol/l), Sodium (mmol/l), urea (mmol/l), leukocytes, ECG, state of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, temperature and acidity. All indicators were assessed in points (from 1 to 4 depending on the degree of their deviation):

1-10 – compensated state (prognosis for life is favorable)

11-29 – subcompensated state (borderline state)

30-44 – decompensated state (prognosis for life is unfavorable)

The proposed algorithm, which is based on numbering criteria, eliminates empiricism when choosing a treatment method for severe liver injuries in unstable patients at risk of developing coagulopathy and multiple organ failure, makes it possible to accurately determine indications for “damage control”, use this technique at the right time, recognize and prevent possible complications in advance, as well as predict the outcome of the disease. The strategy proposed above combines the strengths of programmed relaparotomy and the standard damage control technique for lesions. Step-by-step surgical treatment provides a chance to fully use modernized intensive care syndromic treatment, as well as prosthetic organ function in order to combat the systemic inflammatory response, which is not amenable to drug

and physiotherapeutic stimulation of intestinal paresis. The use of this strategy reduced mortality - from 53.3% to 19.5%.

Conclusions:

1. Multi-stage “damage control” surgical tactics for isolated and combined severe liver injuries is an effective method for unstable patients at risk of developing coagulopathy and multiple organ failure.
2. The use of the “damage control” technique helped reduce the mortality rate from acute pathology of the abdominal organs from 53.3% to 19.5%.

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